

Corporate Knowledge Communication and Knowledge Communication Difficulties

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Abstract—Communication is an important factor and a prop in directing corporate activities efficiently, in ensuring the flow of knowledge which is necessary for the continuity of the institution, in creating a common language in the institution, in transferring corporate culture and ultimately in corporate success. The idea of transmitting the knowledge among the workers in a healthy manner has revived knowledge communication. Knowledge communication can be defined as the act of mutual creation and communication of intuitions, assessments, experiences and capabilities, as long as maintained effectively, can provide advantages such as corporate continuity, access to corporate objectives and making true administrative decisions. Although the benefits of the knowledge communication to corporations are known, and the necessary worth and care is given, some hardships may arise which makes it difficult or even block it. In this article, difficulties that prevent knowledge communication will be discussed and solutions will be proposed.

Keywords—Corporate knowledge communication, knowledge communication, knowledge communication barriers

I. INTRODUCTION

COMMUNICATION which is the compulsory condition for man's physical, intellectual and social activities [6] can be described as a transfer or exchange, in order to deal with emotions, ideas, feelings, opinions and knowledge [10]. Disruptions that may occur internal and external communication and barriers that may affect the success of the corporation to be effective; communication is one of the main factors in achieving managerial and corporate events [1].

Developments in communications technologies, has led to a rapid increase in knowledge. This situation, has made knowledge that does not lose its value any time an indispensable element, for individuals and corporations in particular. Corporations, who understand the importance and necessity of the knowledge, try to evaluate the knowledge and knowledge assets in their hands in the best way. It is required for assessing the knowledge when needed and to produce the knowledge within the corporation; it is also needed to make available and most importantly to share, in other words to transpose. The stand out of concepts of knowledge and communication has revived the concept of *knowledge communication*. Intuition, assessments, and with the experience and capabilities delivered as a mutual act of creation can be described as [8] knowledge communication, and continuity of the institution can be carried out, to achieve corporate objectives and can provide benefits such as granting the right managerial decisions, if used effectively.

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However, increasing the value and importance of knowledge for corporate communications, cannot prevent from happening the difficulties which make difficult or even preventing the process of knowledge communication.

II. CONCEPT OF COMMUNICATION

Communication, a group that connects people and their social interaction is the event that the balance and harmony in the agreements [1] and it is the mutual sharing of meaning through symbols [10]. All corporate decisions and actions in maintaining effective delivery of qualified and experience, intuition and technical knowledge transfer within the corporation requires effective and efficient manner [8]. It is possible to achieve corporate goals with employee cooperation and communications. Therefore, communication, or to the employees informing them about the activities and atmosphere of its own business processes, giving corporations the opportunity to develop the purpose and objectives, the emergence of adequate capacity and encourages creative thinking [1].

Communication is the individual's acquiring knowledge, experience and unattended boiler react accordingly to develop attitudes and behaviors can be thought of as a process [10]. The communication process constitutes a loop. This cycle starts with the message coded and sent to the receiver, the encoded message is sent to the receiver via a medium. To interpret the message of the person, takes it and reacts accordingly. Responses are sent back to the source in the form of notification. Responses to initiate a new process of the source so that the issues of communication and the communication process continue in this manner until interrupted.

III. KNOWLEDGE COMMUNICATION

Knowledge communication, face to face with the vehicle-based interactions or how the resulting knowledge (how to handle a task), why knowledge (a patient with a complex cause-effect relationship), what knowledge (results of a test), and knowledge of who (with others in the experience) as determines the types of knowledge to successfully transfer. Knowledge communication, intuition, assessments, and with the experience and capabilities delivered as a mutual act of creation can be defined as [8]. Therefore, any transmission of knowledge, knowledge communication to be considered, and a two-way communication is the mutual interaction can be said that should happen [1].

Knowledge communication, context, and the basic assumptions of the past because it requires the transmission of communication knowledge (events, numbers, facts, developments, etc.) or emotions (fears, hopes, doubts and commitments, etc.) are more. Also, requires the

communication of personal intuition and experience. In knowledge communication, information and emotions are transmitted. However, a certain type, as well as their context and in this context consists of re-regulation of intuition, the creation of new perspectives and new skills can be used in obtaining [8].

IV. KNOWLEDGE COMMUNICATION BARRIERS

To create behavior or an idea, to transfer the message to forward facing is defined as the basic purpose of communication, people learn by doing, and will accept messages sent to influence them and to guide them to a specific behavior. To ensure effective communication must have certain features that are essential elements that make up the communication process. According to Dawson excellent, effective and quality communications between a communications utopia because people, consciously or unconsciously deteriorating due to a number of emerging or misinterpreted [1]. Therefore, although sometimes with communication features needed items not provided the requested effective communication [4].

Factors that cause this condition and prevent the knowledge communication, the knowledge elements that make up the communication process as a person, knowledge, communication channel, and context can be evaluated under the headings. Factors that prevent knowledge communication from Eppler [8], adapted the classification of the factors that prevent knowledge communication in the Muller [12] were used.

A. Barriers Caused by People

People related to the obstacles, is one of the barriers to knowledge communication. The formation of the source and the receiver of the communication process, people make it necessary to examine the impediments of two parts.

1. Barriers Related to the Source

It is the source through the communication process components which start the sequence. The source of the message and the receiver's feedback encoder is a party waiting to be found. Existing knowledge, experience and communication environment according to warnings from the moment describe the environment, as determined by the mental messages by encrypting the channel and the means chosen by the buyer sends [10]. Obstacles related to the source are given below:

a. Indifference to the sharing of knowledge: At the beginning of the obstacles encountered in communicating knowledge that individual are reluctant to share knowledge. Professional advancement of knowledge as a force to cause the award or the promotion of knowledge sharing to prevent. The power of knowledge to people who own stores of knowledge will be maintained, considering lose share in the value of knowledge. In addition, individual goals, personal relationships, and concerns, may lead to reluctance in sharing knowledge and intuition [9].

b. Lack of the ability to share knowledge: We evaluate other people's situations or events, such as his own presumption, and often consider the case of error (False consensus effect). This is closely related to the other barrier, projectionism. Projectionism, the other party to understand the subject in assuming that he has the same level of knowledge [9]. One of the important elements of the transmission of knowledge, individual properties is owned by the person. The ability to share knowledge and knowledge of the source, coding and sending the message that will be effective and meaningful way so that the message can easily be coded, the receiver is able to create the desired effect. Otherwise, the encoded message is incomplete and inadequate, readily understandable correctly or may cause a different behavior [1]. Knowledge sharing is a problem with other knowledge related to the ability to stifle the message detail (overloading the communication with the details). Technical terms and jargon of professional use large amounts of knowledge can lead to communication problems [8].

c. The receiver's ideas about the source: The receiver's ideas about the source, is one of the major obstacles is caused by people. Personal goals, feelings, values and habits, influencing the formulation of symbols that make up the message and incoming messages to individuals may lead to negative or indifferent attitude. The receiver's attitude toward the source, the confidence and belief in the evaluation of source messages in the future are important factors [4]. Therefore, resource, knowledge, experiences, history and physical condition due to characteristics such as trust and reputation on the receiver of the communication process becomes difficult the realization of high-quality format [1].

2. Barriers Related to the Receiver

The receiver gives the effectiveness of constructive communication, solving and evaluating the person taking the source encodes the meaning of the communication process as is a lot of important. Barriers related to the receiver and can be examined under four headings:

a. Indifference to assimilate the new knowledge: The receiver to contact the person who is related to the receiver at the beginning of the obstacles that are involuntary and indifferent. There are several reasons for disinterest. Some of them come from outside the institution solely for the knowledge on the various reasons to reject others, and refuses to trust the knowledge produced within the corporation. On the other hand due to the personal characteristics of people who do not accept the advice is to receive and share knowledge. In addition, the knowledge within the corporation who do not accept obsolete and do not want to renew themselves, can be found in some groups [9]. These people have passed the state of defense against new knowledge and reluctant to acquire new knowledge.

b. Perception failure: Luhmann's (1975) perception, sense organs organize and interpret the data received with the surrounding objects and events in the process of signification. In this process, the individual's situation, values, needs and

expectations of the individual, social and cultural environment grew, individual knowledge, experience plays an active role in, and factors such as physical characteristics. These factors, selection and evaluation are usually referred to as a filter or measure Cutler [10]. Communication plays an important role in the process of detection of each message; the transmitter consists of detection and the detection result of the communication process acts as a filter [4].

c. The disability to keep the new knowledge: Lack of knowledge or knowledge obtained from the receiver's particular to the wrong reasons such as inexperience with Communicate in interpretation and knowledge to be closed against the recommendations of this kind can lead to obstruction.

d. The receiver's ideas about the source: One of the obstacles related to the receiver, and her disbelief of the resource, such as a lack of buyer confidence in the negative cases. Negative thoughts, is an important factor in preventing the establishment of effective communication. Negatively related to the receiver receiving the notices referred to it because of the ear, blocking a strong opinion, Cassandra syndrome is called [9]. Do not take into account the value of the source and the receiver does not need knowledge of data communication is very difficult, mutual relations and trust can be damaged [8].

B. Barriers Caused by Knowledge

Institutions, competition, innovation, creativity and productivity in order to achieve inner and outer circles of knowledge are the institutional processes that they use has become an important and a priority. Innovation, creativity and come up with strategies for today's competitive structure, corporate knowledge is considered as a strategic asset and a factor of production. In this context, knowledge communication barriers in the knowledge source can be examined under three headings:

1. Limitations arising from the nature of knowledge: Knowledge has some features as dynamic, complex, personal and flexible. These features, as well as some limitations bring the benefits they provide.

2. Ambiguity: Knowledge communication uncertainties, including the knowledge communication in one of the obstacles. Perception is based on the uncertainty of meaning and structure of the message, as well as the person perceives to be closely related to the properties lies in the [10]. Ambiguities, the meaning of the message, waiting for response and uncertainty about the response time, discrepancies between knowledge contained in the message with the required knowledge and content of the message clear and simple ways, such as may occur in the absence [1].

3. Failure in compliance with regulations for the purpose: Knowledge and communication that serves as a communication bridge between the source and target largely determines the success of the message that [10]. Therefore, a knowledge message should be remarkable and be set up with a common language. It must create motivation on the receiver

and should not include unnecessary words. It should be clear and understandable and able to contact the receiver in accordance with the value judgments. Also the subject that interests the encoder and the receiver should be closely associated.

C. Barriers Caused by Communication Channel

Communication occurs, the message being sent is sent by sense due to the perception and interpretation. Contact the source and the receiver will take place when they take the same meaning to the message. Therefore, the selected communication channels and tools to achieve the objectives of this communication are of great importance. To whom, for what purpose, what is delivered, to be used is determined by the channel and means of communication [10]. Therefore, the communications problems that may occur, directly affects the knowledge communication. Prevents the channel from this context can be examined in three chapters:

1. Connection failure: The departments within the authority, departments and units who are able, in a structure will be easily organized, corporate communication; communication of the knowledge will not be realized or will take place very difficult.

2. Noise: Noise, affecting the normal flow of communication and the flow of communication are factors that glitch. Coding of the message to resolve the noise that affects the whole process of communication, the message is correct or prevent the receipt of a complete [6], [1].

3. Data loss: Corporate hierarchy and formal structure of the corporation, communication barriers can pose. Corporations, center or turns into more complex structures, communication channels, channel extension and obstacles arise. Technical errors in communication channels and the riots posts loss, to postpone or cause misunderstanding [4]. Information overload is called the excess burden of knowledge is worthless, and the ordinary as well as knowledge for the institution may lead to missing an important and valuable knowledge. On the other hand the use of terminology that is incorrect or missing may result data loss in interpersonal communication.

D. Barriers Caused by Context

Context, communication takes place the physical, social, psychological and temporal environment. Every communication, historical, technological, psychological and teleological conditions occur when shaped. All the elements brought together by an experienced in the past, gives rise to the context of communication [6]. The format and content of communication as a variable affecting the context of the message determines how to interpret expand significantly [10]. In this context, the context can be evaluated from the block of three chapters:

1. Barriers related to the structure, organization and functioning of the society: Society is composed of culturally similar groups. These groups are connected to a common culture, common language use, and extends deeper into the cultural similarities [7]. Communication between the only

people is not achieved in their social context and in light of what we sense takes place between the worlds and cultural icons. Therefore, communication, mutual interactions with the people who have the same or similar symbols and the symbols for both parties for playing something similar to occur. In this respect, icons, messages, and events for people giving meaning, interpretation tools [10]. The lack of people with common symbols or icons, such as the common things or situations, knowledge can lead to communication barriers.

2. *Barriers related to the structure, organization and functioning of the corporate:* Corporate structure is one of the important factors that affect the sharing of knowledge communication. In organization and process of corporate, many communication barriers may occur at different levels. Corporate barriers can be summarized corporate size, attitude of managers, management style, corporate culture, organization of corporate and amount of knowledge sharing as six chapters [1]:

a. *Corporate size:* As increase of operating areas and the number of members will cause corporate communications difficulties and communication systems, more are becoming more complex. The size and complexity of organizations can pose a major obstacle to transmission required knowledge to the members timely, fully and correctly. While the size of the corporate may destroy message and the complexity may impact the effectiveness of the message [4].

b. *Managers' attitudes and behaviors:* One of the obstacles related to corporate structure is the attitudes and behaviors of managers. Knowledge, knowledge sharing and knowledge communication required and the importance of not showing interest, not to support the necessary organizational infrastructure, not to develop policies about knowledge sharing and knowledge communication such as an incorrect or incomplete attitudes and behaviors exhibited by managers.

c. *Corporate's management style:* Management style is shaped by managers' attitudes and behaviors. Defects in the corporate's management style, corporate knowledge is insufficient or lack of communication policies, employee trust and respect each other causes a lack of proper knowledge communication so that the working environment and employees around common goals. Besides corporate's management style is shaping the corporate culture.

d. *Corporate culture:* Corporate culture is the sum of shared meanings, feelings, insights, philosophies, ideologies, expectations and attitudes. Shared fundamental values and norms, affects the behavior of individuals and directs them [2]. Therefore inappropriate corporate culture can lead to some of the obstacles for knowledge sharing and knowledge communication. Fear of being criticized by executives or other employees is one of these obstacles. As awarding is given to the individual efforts in knowledge sharing, people stock their knowledge and only share worthless knowledge so this situation can lead to reduced quality of the knowledge [2].

e. *Organization of the corporate:* Organizations, departments, units and groups in corporate communications with the time and manner that may cause loss of data can be organized. Lack of appropriate communication channels, preventing communication between the organization and the informal solid organizational structure [3] of knowledge can lead to knowledge communication barriers. On the other hand the knowledge has been exposed to unnecessary interference, corruption or unnecessary to go completions, knowledge decreases the effectiveness of knowledge communication [1].

f. *Amount of knowledge sharing:* Amount of knowledge sharing is another obstacle in knowledge communication. Excessive complacency or dissatisfaction with the transmitted knowledge may lead the receiver, the transmitted knowledge is required at the receiver, unease, or misunderstandings can lead to loss of time and effort.

The last barrier derived from the context is diversity of people's role and status:

3. *The role and status differences:* Social status in society can be reached with the use of valid measures of social value of a building, an assessment. Describes the place where that person's social status compared with others. The concept of social role, status, or fill a particular position, represents the expected behavior of person. Social roles, many of the criteria used to measure an individual's status as one of the patterns of behavior consists of both open and closed. Each role is a social content, content is always linked with other social roles and all roles in a more or less generalized, and each culture was standardized [7]. Often determined by status and role of social relations and the role and status is one of the obstacles related to the context. Role in determining the direction and frequency of communication and status differences [10] knowledge communication are important factors leading to obstruction.

V. KNOWLEDGE COMMUNICATION SOLUTIONS FOR BARRIERS ENCOUNTERED

In order to produce solutions to the obstacles encountered in the context of first contact knowledge, communications should be taken into account. Moreover the source of knowledge to identify the obstacles to overcome communication barriers and develop solutions accordingly will be the right approach [4]. In this context, the possible solutions to the barriers encountered in knowledge communication, elements of knowledge communication are given below:

A. *Solutions to barriers caused by person:* To overcome the obstacles caused by person, first of all corporate knowledge policy and corporate knowledge culture should be created and developed. Thus the indifference to the knowledge needed can be precluded. On the other hand in order to increase the ability to keep the knowledge to work, people should be open to new ideas, opinions and attitudes of corporate employees, and employees must be trained to be flexible in the direction should be given time to learn new knowledge [11]. In addition, to eliminate the barriers caused by different perceptions of empathic communication efforts should be made in-house.

Knowledge sharing is against apathy needed to encourage the sharing of knowledge and knowledge sharing practices be implemented should be awarded. Implicit knowledge found in someone who lacks the ability to share knowledge, various studies should be done to attribute implicit knowledge to the corporate.

B. Solutions to barriers caused by knowledge: The coding of knowledge in order to overcome the limitations arising from the nature of knowledge, transfer, evaluation and integration of processes associated with knowledge such as the need to focus on issues at the corporate level [12]. To overcome the ambiguity, statement difficulties that caused confusion and incoherence should be abandoned. The knowledge should be related with the content and expressed clear and understandable. Intelligibility of knowledge depends on the source's knowledge, experience, skills, values and belief systems. For this reason, the improvements of these features are very important [1].

C. Solutions to barriers caused by communication channels: To overcome connection failure, internal processes that will allow the transmission of knowledge and appropriate infrastructures must be established to facilitate this process [12]. The correct communication channel and knowledge communication tools to provide feedback and two-way communication should be chosen. According to Sorrels (1984) by selecting a communication channel, which is a high potential for feedback, and sent the message that best appeals to the buyer as soon as possible, issues should be taken as the correct way forward [1]. Technical and technological problems with the communications obstacles that can cause problems such as noise and the rapid collapse of communication should be identified and eliminated. On the other hand mutual intelligibility should be checked on a regular basis.

D. Solutions to barriers arising from the context: Barriers arising from the context stem from individual, corporate and social relations and the environment these relationships occur, as well as their, corporate, cultural and structural rules, and regulations. Therefore, these structures should be considered in determining the solution pathways [12]. Corporate structure should be reserved corporate culture that involved knowledge, should be a specific time and space for knowledge sharing and knowledge communication [11]. On the other hand, some corporate communication strategies can be developed and used with developing communication technologies. Thus, the technology could also have an open, intensive and multi-way communication to support, encourage, and can be used to be prospered [5]. In such cases, departments, units and groups reorganize according to the needs of corporate communication is required.

Barriers due to differences in the role and status of individual errors and help requests for the solution treated with tolerance, people not lose their status because they do not know. On the other hand certain groups of knowledge and knowledge is not a recognized privilege not a hierarchical structure of the product and in particular the status of those

ideas should be emphasized that more important and valuable [11]. Finally, the corporate should be encouraged knowledge communication and communication barriers between departments so as to prevent the mobility should be provided, such as internal displacement should be taken [5].

VI. CONCLUSION

Effective knowledge communication with the knowledge needed by corporate management, quick, economical and can be obtained correctly, the correct decisions can be taken and an effective corporate governance will be provided. In addition, the expectations of employees and identifying problems and opportunities will be provided on issues such as the proceeding was resolved them [1]. On the other hand with knowledge communication, common understanding and synergy will be created, employees' trust in them, develop confidence in his teammates so that the desire to reinforce institutional cooperation and collaboration. Knowledge sharing and knowledge communication with the creation of a suitable working environment with more open channels of communication and knowledge sharing and knowledge communication is realized more and more high-quality knowledge [5]. As a result, in institutions the effective knowledge communication is used to assure continuity, to achieve corporate objectives, such as the benefits to be able to provide accurate and timely administrative decisions.

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